

SCIENTIFIC AND LEGAL ASPECTS OF UNDERSTANDING THE ESSENCE OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY

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Abstract

This article analyzes the scientific and legal approaches to understanding the essence of intellectual property, its content and legal nature. The main doctrinal positions regarding the concept of intellectual property are examined comparatively, including the property (ownership) concept and the concept of absolute (exclusive) rights. The article also explores the place of intellectual activity results within the system of civil law objects, their distinguishing characteristics from tangible objects, and the mechanisms of legal protection. The economic, legal, and social significance of intellectual property law, as well as its role in modern market relations, are substantiated. The research findings are intended to serve the further improvement of the intellectual property institution and the development of its legal regulatory mechanisms.

Keywords: intellectual property, intellectual property law, absolute right, property concept, civil law, results of intellectual activity, legal protection, means of individualization, innovation, legal institution.

The institution of intellectual property has repeatedly been compelled, throughout its formation and development, to demonstrate in practice that it is an effective legal instrument for accelerating scientific and technological progress, ensuring economic growth, and stimulating innovative activity. Even today, intellectual rights are recognized as one of the key factors in the formation and development of national innovation systems. These rights serve to support innovative processes across all sectors — from the activities of individual organizations or institutions to the economic development of entire countries and regions.

At the same time, practical experience in the field of intellectual property demonstrates that attitudes toward this institution are not always uniform. In some cases, divergent views have formed regarding the intellectual property institution itself, the mechanisms for its protection and use, as well as the existing approaches and methods for resolving conflicts of

interest in this domain. This has given rise to complex disputes in the processes of creating, using, and commercializing intellectual activity results.

One of the key consequences of these contradictions is the failure to develop sufficient interest and incentives for the legal protection of intellectual activity results and their introduction into economic circulation. As a result, the effectiveness of innovative activity declines, the transfer of scientific developments into practice slows down, and the pace of innovative development across various branches of the economy weakens.

Results of contemporary scholarly research demonstrate that the failure of market participants to achieve the expected outcomes from the intellectual property institution is largely attributable to the unsystematic utilization of its potential. Furthermore, the reduction of intellectual property activities exclusively to patenting or legal protection measures, as well as the tendency to overabsolutize the significance of rights in a specific intellectual property object, are among the principal causes of the existing problems.

In this connection, among the key tasks of state governance in the intellectual property sphere at the present stage is ensuring the effective utilization of intellectual activity results across various sectors of the economy and social life. Moreover, harmonizing relations among the principal stakeholders in the intellectual property sphere — namely, the state, business entities, and authors — balancing their interests, and forming effective cooperation mechanisms aimed at advancing the national innovative economy are also matters of pressing importance.

State policy in the field of intellectual property must be directed toward further improving existing opportunities, creating effective mechanisms for their utilization, and enhancing the competitiveness of national production. This policy must also encompass the tasks of stimulating import substitution, supporting priority sectors of the economy, and ensuring innovative development.

Each year, thousands of intellectual property objects are registered by the state. However, despite the fact that a significant portion of the rights to these objects rests with the state, the issues of effectively engaging these objects in economic circulation and deriving substantial economic benefit from them remain incompletely resolved. This limits the possibility of achieving the expected outcomes in the administrative, economic, and social spheres.

Furthermore, the further improvement of legal regulation of relations in the field of intellectual property should also provide impetus for the modernization of organizational and

managerial mechanisms. In some instances, these mechanisms continue to operate on the basis of administrative and command-based methods. In the context of the modern economy, it is of great importance to introduce market-oriented and efficiency-driven approaches to intellectual property management.

The diversity of legal, economic, and social relations within the intellectual property institution, its internal contradictions, the strategic significance of the intellectual property market for national development, and the numerous problems associated with its advancement all give rise to a pressing need for an in-depth study of the essence and content of the intellectual property institution. For this reason, the comprehensive research of the legal, economic, and organizational mechanisms ensuring the effective functioning of the intellectual property institution, and the elaboration of scientifically grounded directions for their improvement, constitutes one of the important tasks of the present time.

In contemporary scholarly literature, two main conceptual approaches have emerged regarding the essence and legal nature of the concept of intellectual property. The first approach interprets intellectual property as a specific manifestation of the property institution, considering it appropriate to disclose its content through the category of "property" and its legal characteristics. The second approach treats intellectual property as a separate legal institution, substantiating the need to explain its content through the category of "rights" — that is, the system of rights arising in relation to the results of intellectual activity.

Proponents of the first concept emphasize the need to consolidate the notion of intellectual property at the legislative level in close connection with property rights. According to them, the active normative use of this concept — including its broad reflection in recommendatory and doctrinal documents — serves to further clarify its legal nature.¹ Certain scholars further argue that equating, in terms of legal nature, property rights and rights to intellectual property objects is appropriate, arriving at the conclusion that "the systematic consolidation of rights to various forms of property must not be limited exclusively to tangible objects."²

¹Diundin, V.D. (2014) *Intelektualna vlasnist yak holovna skladova intelektualnoho potentsialu* [Intellectual property as the main component of intellectual potential]. *Efektivna ekonomika*, no. 5, pp. 29–37.

²Nosik, Yu. V. (2007) *Prava na komertsiinu taiemnytsiu v Ukraini: Monohrafiia* [Rights to commercial secrets in Ukraine: Monograph]. Kyiv: KNT, p. 7.

Another group of scholars identifies the commonality between both constructions, citing the feature of object-boundedness as the main criterion. In their view, the idea that "a thing cannot exist without a right" holds significant importance in the legal system, and expressions such as "the obligation to transfer a thing to another person as property" are explained precisely by the transfer of a right within a legal relationship.³

At the same time, within the currently operative normative-legal system, the concept of "intellectual property right" is primarily consolidated as a legal term, whereas the term "intellectual property" itself, as an independent category, has not been fully developed conceptually. In this context, the primary legal definition relies on the provisions of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan. According to the Code, intellectual property right is the right of a person to the result of his intellectual or creative activity, or to another intellectual property object established by law. This right comprises a set of personal non-property and property rights, the content of which is defined by the respective laws in relation to specific objects.⁴

Another group of scholars considers this concept and its content to be insufficiently precise and not adequately substantiated from a scientific standpoint. They propose interpreting the concept of intellectual property in its generally accepted sense — namely, as a special right arising in relation to the results of human intellectual activity. These results emerge in scientific, artistic, industrial, and other fields, manifest as objects of civil-legal relations, and constitute a specific portion of relations pertaining to the legal protection of each result of intellectual and creative activity.⁵

In this regard, the results of intellectual activity, as intangible goods, remain with their creators and may be used by other persons only with their consent and agreement.⁶

³Yuskaev, V.B. (2010) *Intelektualna vlasnist: navchalnyi posibnyk u dvokh chastynakh* [Intellectual property: textbook in two parts]. Sumy: Vydavnytstvo SumDU, Pt. 2, p. 54.

⁴Okyulov, O. (2000) *Pravovoy status intellektualnoy sobstvennosti* [Legal status of intellectual property]. Tashkent: TGYU. Doctoral dissertation. pp. 14, 36.

⁵Imomov, N.F. (2011) *Intellektual mulk huquqining yangi ob'ektlari* [New objects of intellectual property law]. Ed. O. Oqyulov. Tashkent: TDYU Press, pp. 37–38.

⁶Nasriev, I. (2006) *Shaxsiy nomulkiy huquqlar mazmuni, ularni amalga oshirish va kengaytirish istiqbollarini fuqarolik huquqiy masalalari* [Civil law issues of personal non-property rights, their exercise and prospects of expansion]. Abstract of doctoral dissertation. Tashkent, p. 51.

It is noteworthy that representatives of economic sciences make extensive use of the term "intellectual property," yet they interpret "property" not in a legal sense but rather as an economic category, equating it with a resource or asset.⁷

Moreover, some scholars argue that it is not entirely justified to speak of a right of possession in the current context. In their view, intellectual property objects, unlike tangible things, have an almost "intangible" character, which limits the possibility of exercising actual dominion (factual possession) over them.⁸

According to another view, the right of disposition in relation to intellectual property objects should be interpreted as the possibility of determining the terms of access to such an object.⁹

As scholars note, in circumstances where a work may be simultaneously used by multiple persons, the traditional mechanisms of protecting the right of possession do not apply, and the possibility of bringing a vindication claim is absent.¹⁰

Some scholars also emphasize that intellectual property rights always have a broader content than the specific object to which they pertain. For instance, the use of a designation that is confusingly similar to a trademark is also assessed as an infringement of rights.¹¹

⁷Vasylyev, O.V. (2016) Intelektualna vlasnist: vyznachennia, struktura ta rol u suchasnykh ekonomichnykh umovakh [Intellectual property: definition, structure and role in modern economic conditions]. *Ekonomika i suspilstvo*, no. 6, pp. 53–57.

⁸Yakubov, A.N. (2022) Kibermakonda raqamli mulk huquqi va uni huquqiy tartibga solish [Digital property rights in cyberspace and their legal regulation]. Abstract of doctoral dissertation. Tashkent, p. 12.

⁹Yemelianov, V.M., Yevtushenko, O.N., Behlytsia, V.P., Andriash, V.I., Lushhahyna, T.V. (2021) Teoretyko-metodolohichni osnovy publichnoi vlady i upravlinnia v Ukraini: monohrafiia [Theoretical and methodological foundations of public authority and governance in Ukraine: monograph]. Mykolaiv, p. 109.

¹⁰Yuldashov, A.A. Mualliflik huquqini muhofaza qilishning shartnomaviy-huquqiy asoslari [Contractual and legal bases for the protection of copyright]. Abstract of PhD dissertation, p. 14.

¹¹Spitsyna, H.O., Hordeichuk, A.O. (2020) Osobennosti sovremennoy klassifikatsii ob'ektov prava intellektualnoy sobstvennosti [Features of the modern classification of intellectual property objects]. *Naukovyi visnyk Dnipropetrovskoho derzhavnoho universytetu vnutrishnikh sprav*, no. 3, pp. 58–64.

Certain scholars, when interpreting property relations, understand ownership as the belonging of any material and intangible goods (things and results of intellectual activity) to a specific person, which may even extend beyond the subjects of legal relations.¹²

However, according to V. Zhukov, the term "intellectual property" is of a conditional nature and does not fully correspond to the actual content of legal reality — that is, the institution of property rights.¹³

At the same time, contemporary researchers note that a certain similarity exists between the constructions of intellectual property and tangible property. Specifically, in their view, possession manifests as possession of the material carrier containing the intellectual property object; use means the practical utilization of such carriers; and disposition denotes the possibility of determining the legal fate of the intellectual property object.¹⁴

Furthermore, it is emphasized that both constructions are characterized by absolute rights, and that identical legal instruments may be employed in the dynamics of property rights. These instruments include contracts of sale, exchange, pledge, and other agreements that may constitute the subject matter of property rights.¹⁵

It should be noted that the norms of the Civil Code of Uzbekistan employ the term "intellectual property" and establish its definition in Article 97. At the same time, Section IV of the Code specifically stipulates that intellectual property rights and property rights are not interrelated (Article 1038). In particular, it is stated that the transfer of the right to an intellectual property object to another person does not entail the transfer of the ownership right to the thing, and conversely, the transfer of ownership of a thing does not automatically result in the transfer of rights to the intellectual property object.

¹²Matviichuk, V.K., Chuhaienko, Yu.O., Savenkov, O.I. (2013) *Intelektualna vlasnist yak dzherelo innovatsiynoho rozvytku natsionalnogo hospodarstva: monohrafiia* [Intellectual property as a source of innovative development of the national economy: monograph]. Kyiv: Natsionalna akademiia upravlinnia, p. 298.

¹³Zhukov, V. (2000) *Rynok intelektualnoy sobstvennosti i novyy Grazhdanskiy kodeks Ukrainy* [The intellectual property market and the new Civil Code of Ukraine]. *Intellektualnaya sobstvennost*, no. 3, p. 44.

¹⁴Demchenko, T.S. (2008) *Nedobrosovestnost zayavitelya v zakonodatelstve o tovarnykh znakakh: monografiya* [Bad faith of the applicant in trademark legislation: monograph]. Kyiv: Lazuryt-Polyhraf, p. 15.

¹⁵Didkivskyi, M.I. (2011) *Mizhnarodnyi transfer tekhnolohii: navch. posib.* [International technology transfer: textbook]. Kyiv: Znannia, p. 49.

From the foregoing, it may be concluded that the full application of the property rights concept to the results of intellectual activity is not always appropriate. This is because the result of intellectual activity is not a tangible thing but a legal object of an intangible nature. Although it may be expressed in a specific material form, its content is not intrinsically linked to the material carrier and is independent from it.

In other words, in the event of the sale of an intellectual activity result or the transfer of rights thereto to another person, the author or rights holder does not lose all rights to it entirely — which differs significantly from the property rights regime applicable to tangible objects. For this reason, it is emphasized that a clear distinction must be maintained between the legal regime applicable to material objects and the legal regime applicable to intangible results of intellectual activity.

Furthermore, among the principal reasons for employing the property rights construction in relation to intellectual property is the widespread belief that this legal model offers the possibility of affording the maximum protection to rights holders.

With regard to the interpretation of intellectual property as an absolute right, a number of approaches have been put forward by scholars. In their view, certain inconsistencies exist between the recommendatory provisions of the international convention establishing the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and the norms of national legislation; in practice, the concept of intellectual property is in many instances explained through the category of "property rights."

In addition, many international treaties ratified by our state also characterize the concept of intellectual property precisely through the concept of property rights. For instance, the Convention Establishing the World Intellectual Property Organization contains a definition of intellectual property; pursuant to Article 2(viii) thereof, intellectual property encompasses all rights relating to literary, artistic, and scientific works, inventions, industrial designs, trademarks, and all intellectual activity in the fields of production, science, literature, and art.¹⁶

¹⁶Melnyk, O.M. (2003) Subiekt prava intelektualnoi vlasnosti ta yoho tsyvilno-pravovyi status [The subject of intellectual property law and its civil law status]. Kharkiv: Vydavnytstvo Natsionalnoho universytetu vnutrishnikh sprav, p. 156.

According to certain scholars, this approach gives rise to particular contradictions — the boundaries between the rights that are the object of legal regulation and the objects themselves become blurred, and as a result they are equated with one another.¹⁷

Moreover, certain scholars point out that as a result of various amendments introduced into legislative norms, absolute rights that had been included among the objects of civil rights were incorrectly excluded. At the same time, they argue that a specific legal construction has been formulated which contemplates the possibility of elements — not constituting objects of rights — possessing a reverse effect or capacity.¹⁸ Another group of scholars, conversely, notes that the content of these legal norms is connected with the understanding of intellectual property results as objects that are independently incapable of participating in civil transactions, whereas the rights arising with respect to these results possess such a capacity.¹⁹

Based on the specific characteristics outlined above, it would be appropriate to introduce corresponding amendments at the legislative level. In particular, within the Civil Code of Uzbekistan, there is a need to clearly define the concept of "intellectual property" and to further clarify the category of "intellectual property right." In this connection, it may be stated that although intellectual property rights differ to some degree from property rights in relation to the results of intellectual activity, they functionally perform tasks similar to those fulfilled by property rights in relation to tangible objects. Consequently, the concept of intellectual property may be characterized as the attitude of the rights holder toward the results of intellectual activity; as an integrated set of the results of human activity in any field, together with the property and non-property rights associated therewith.

It deserves particular emphasis that today the owners of intellectual property are among the primary subjects determining the formation of a new world and international order. This is because knowledge — or intellectual property — and its exploitation for profit constitute the

¹⁷ Mykulonok, I.O. (2005) *Osnovy intelektualnoi vlasnosti: navchalnyi posibnyk* [Fundamentals of intellectual property: textbook]. Kyiv: IVTs Vydavnytstvo Politehnika; Lira-K, p. 5.

¹⁸ Haliantych, M.K. (2003) *Promyslova vlasnist: pravovi zasoby okhorony ta zakhystu: monohrafiia* [Industrial property: legal means of protection: monograph]. Kyiv: NDI pryvatnoho prava i pidpriemnytstva, p. 12.

¹⁹ Boyar, A.O. (2007) *Intelektualna vlasnist: monohrafiia* [Intellectual property: monograph]. Lutsk: RVV Vezha Volynskoho natsionalnoho universytetu imeni Lesi Ukrainky, p. 13.

principal factor ensuring competitiveness and sustainable economic growth.²⁰ Furthermore, intellectual property must be viewed not merely as a legal category but as a system of knowledge that holds value in the present and will continue to do so in the future. It represents a specific asset capable of generating real value in the course of activity. Only those individuals who possess the capacity to develop, implement, and improve existing methods aimed at managing, legally protecting, identifying, acquiring rights to, and making effective use of intellectual property objects can emerge as successful leaders and managers. They must also be able to clearly identify which intellectual property objects are to be preserved and which are to be created — a capacity that ensures their competitiveness and long-term viability.

At present, the concept of intellectual property continues to remain a debated and variously interpreted category in both foreign and national scholarly literature. The diverse views of researchers may be conditionally divided into two main conceptual directions: the property concept and the concept of absolute (exclusive) rights. Proponents of the property concept interpret the rights of a creative product's author by equating them with property rights in relation to tangible objects; in their view, rights to the results of intellectual activity are explained on the basis of the property rights model. Proponents of the concept of absolute rights, by contrast, hold that rights arising in connection with intellectual property must not be equated with property rights and must manifest as independent subjective rights — that is, such rights must by their very nature be exclusive in character. In our view, intellectual property rights in relation to the results of intellectual activity differ from property rights in terms of content and nature, yet they are functionally capable of performing tasks analogous to those performed by property rights in relation to the results of intellectual activity. For this reason, it is appropriate to study the intellectual property institution not within the confines of a single approach alone, but on the basis of a comprehensive methodology. Accounting for legal, economic, philosophical, and managerial approaches will ensure the effectiveness of creating and utilizing the results of intellectual property. On this basis, the concept of intellectual property may be defined as the specific relationship of a rights holder to the results of intellectual activity, including means of individualization. This relationship is of an absolute character, and its

²⁰Polyakov, S.Yu., Kurtov, A.I., Nikitiuk, O.B., Zmievskiy, G.A. Nekotoryye aspekty i printsipy upravleniya intellektualnoy sobstvennostyu v Ukraine [Some aspects and principles of intellectual property management in Ukraine]. Vestnik NTU KhPI, no. 60, p. 73.

content comprises a set of various legal powers conditioned on the characteristics of the object, ensuring corresponding access and absolute protection.

Furthermore, modern society cannot be conceived without the active utilization of the results of intellectual activity. Intellectual property, in turn, serves as the principal foundation of the modern state and all its activities across every field. The results of intellectual activity — including means of individualization — are acquiring ever greater significance, and the continued development of society requires the effective and adequate regulation of rights pertaining to these objects.